

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Gro Haarklou Mathisen

Your email address: gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 25.08.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, data curation, methodology, visualisation

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Evidence-based chemical risk assessments are a large part of my daily work. As the toxicity data are shifting from animal studies to NAMs, I am interested in the development of tools for incorporation of such data as evidence in chemical risk assessments.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "G. Harlow Mathison". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large initial "G".

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Gunn Elisabeth Vist

Your email address: gunn.vist@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (06.06.2023):

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Data curation, Methodology, Writing-Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have no financial interests related to this publication

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am convinced of the benefits of being evidence-based in research. Otherwise, no conflicting interests pertaining to this publication

Signature

Gunn E. Vist

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Declaration of Contributor Interests

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form.

Personal details

Your name: Paul Whaley

Your email address, for contact purposes: paul@whaleyresearch.uk

Date of completion of this form (DD MMM YYYY): 3 February 2023

Contribution to the Research Project

Conceptualisation, methodology, writing - original draft, writing - review and editing, visualisation, supervision

Interests

Place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the SR?		Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially conflict with the objectives of the SR?	
X	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.		Deeply held beliefs or convictions
	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	x	Current and previous research findings or projects
	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	x	Commitments to specific standards or processes
	From litigation or legal cases		Publicly held positions
	From grants		Personal relationships
	Other financial interests	x	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
		x	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
			Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have or am providing consultancy services for: the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) at Johns Hopkins University Bloomberg School of Public Health; Lancaster University, mainly around securing impact of the research I was doing for my PhD (completed 2020); and for Yordas Group, to deliver training in SR methods for EU JRC. I also receive an Honorarium as Editor in Chief for the journal *Evidence-Based Toxicology* (EBT), to which this manuscript is being submitted. I am setting up the Institute for Evidence-Based Toxicology, a non-profit company based in Germany. The company will begin trading in 2023, and I am one of 4 Directors with a 25% share in the business. The work of the company will be providing services relating to evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental health.

In general, my consultancy work is around development and promotion of systematic review methods in environmental health research, delivering training around these methods, and providing editorial services. While relevant to the present work, I am not aware of any way in which these interests could compromise the integrity of the research I am undertaking here.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I have a general public commitment to high quality systematic review methods in support of environmental health policy and decision-making, and am actively involved in a range of projects intended to improve research standards in evidence synthesis. I have developed conduct standards (e.g. COSTER), reporting checklists (e.g. ROSES), and critical appraisal tools (e.g. CREST_Triage, PRIVAT) to support the production of high quality systematic reviews and evidence maps. I am an active member of the GRADE Working Group, an informal UK NGO network promoting good environmental policy in the UK, have a senior role at EBTC that involves promoting SR and other evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental health; similarly, my role at the journal EBT involves high-profile public advocacy for evidence-based approaches to evidence synthesis that includes advocating for the use of study appraisal instruments, of which the present manuscript is an example. In general, I have a strong interest in supporting precautionary, evidence-based approaches to environmental health policy. While relevant to the present work, I am not aware of any way in which these interests could compromise the integrity of the research I am undertaking here, as the standards implied by the work are consistent with those to which I have expressed public commitment.

Signature

SIGNED

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Richard Aubrey White

Your email address: RichardAubrey.White@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 25.28.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology.

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Employed by the Norwegian government at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

Signature

Richard Aubrey White

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Trine Husøy

Your email address: trine.husoy@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 19 06 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualisation, methodology, writing - review and editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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x	Publicly held positions
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Non to declare

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Non to declare

Signature

Tanni Husky

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Heather Ames

Your email address: heather.ames@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 09.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read "Heather J. ...". The signature is written in a cursive style.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Anna Beronius

Your email address: anna.beronius@ki.se

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 22 June 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Review and comment

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

N/A

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Beronius is one of the initiators and developers of the SciRAP tools for data appraisal, which includes a tool for evaluating quality of in vitro toxicity data.

Signature

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Signature page

This document has been electronically signed
using eduSign.

eduSign

Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Emma Di Consiglio

Your email address: emma.diconsiglio@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):03 07 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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The issues described in the paper partially overlap and/or are extremely useful for other projects and/or risk assessment activities (EFSA WG, EU COM), in which I am actively involved, related to the use and development of NAMs.

Signature

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Ingrid L. Druwe

Your email address: druwe.ingrid@epa.gov

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 07/03/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Provided critical review and commentary

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am an employee of the United States Environmental Protection Agency in the Center for Public Health and Environmental Assessments (CPHEA) where I work on IRIS chemical risk assessments and their impact on human health and the environment. Implementation of novel systematic review methods such as those being explored in this manuscript may be incorporated directly or indirectly into the systematic review methodology used by CPHEA.

Signature

Ingrid L. Druwe 07/03/2023

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Thomas Hartung

Your email address: THartung@jhu.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 02 Jul 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Not applicable

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Not applicable

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'A. Maly', is written over the 'Not applicable' text.

Signature

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Sebastian Hoffmann

Your email address: Sebastian.hoffmann@seh-cs.com

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 06.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing; Supervision

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
<input type="checkbox"/> From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input type="checkbox"/> From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/> From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/> From litigation or legal cases	<input type="checkbox"/> Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/> From grants	<input type="checkbox"/> Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/> Other financial interests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

My research interests are assessment of NAM methods and EBT. I fully embrace the principles of evidence-based toxicology.

I am a member of the SOT and of the EBM commission of the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment.

The publication may affect these non-financial interests.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Carlijn Hooijmans

Your email address: Carlijn.hooijmans@radboudumc.nl

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):23062023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Advice on methods

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I do not have any of the listed non financial interests. I am a scientist at the Radboud university of Nijmegen in the Netherlands, and I run the meta research team. A team that focusses on developing, applying and disseminating systematic review methodology across evidence streams, performing meta-research on research rigour and robustness principles and providing education within and beyond the Radboudumc.

Signature

A handwritten signature consisting of a stylized, scribbled initial followed by the name 'Guymans' written in a cursive, handwritten style.

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Kyriaki Machera

Your email address: k.machera@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):08.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above
No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Andy', written in a cursive style.

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Pilar Prieto

Your email address: pilar.prieto-peraita@ec.europa.eu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29 06 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Final review

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'P. In', written over a horizontal line.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Joshua Robinson

Your email address: joshua.robinson@ucsf.edu

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 29 06 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

I have received funding from the National Institutes of Health (NIH) and other sources which support the development and application of in vitro toxicological assessments. Thus, I have

a financial interest in the overall growth of in vitro science field for toxicology and chemical risk assessment.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am a member of the Society of Toxicology and the Society of Birth Defects Research and Prevention. Both of these societies support the development of the in vitro science field for toxicology and chemical risk assessment.

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'JFR', written over a light blue horizontal line.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Erwin L Roggen

Your email address: elro@3rsmc.onmicrosoft.com

Date of completion of form (19.06.2023):

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

As member of the PARC SAG

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> no Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input type="checkbox"/> no Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Not relevant

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, consisting of several loops and a long horizontal stroke at the end.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Nicolas Roth

Your email address: nicolas.roth@unibas.ch

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 07.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Not Applicable

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

I am an Associate Editor of systematic reviews and systematic evidence maps at Environment International – I have an interest in developing tools, instruments, methods and standards that contribute to advance systematic review theory and practice.

As a regulatory toxicology expert and chemical risk assessor at the Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology, Basel, Switzerland, I have a direct interest in developing an instrument that I can use to in my daily workflow.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'N. J. van'.

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Eliana Spilioti

Your email address: e.spilioti@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 08/06/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above
No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

Notes

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Anastasia Spyropoulou

Your email address: a.spyropoulou@bpi.gr

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):08.06.2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

No financial interests.

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

This journal paper/work falls under my current and previous scientific interests and projects.

Signature

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Olga Tcheremenskaia

Your email address: olga.tcheremenskaia@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 03/07/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?	Non-financial interests Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?
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	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Being involved in several institutional activities and projects under OECD (on AOP, IATA, in silico NAMs) that aim to increase the confidence in NAMs with the purpose of using them in risk assessment procedures, the issues described in the papers partially overlap with my other interests and are of great interest for my current work.

Signature

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "Olga Tcheumina". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large initial 'O'.

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Emanuela Testai

Your email address: emanuela.testai@iss.it

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY):03/07/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Writing - Review & Editing; Funding acquisition

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	From employment or provision of services, such as directorships, consultancy, honoraria, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From intellectual property, such as patents, copyrights, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From investments such as shares, stocks, other financial instruments, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	From litigation or legal cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	From grants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other financial interests

Non-financial interests

Do you have any of the following interests that could potentially influence or be affected by the publication?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Deeply held beliefs or convictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Current and previous research findings or projects
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commitments to specific standards or processes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Publicly held positions
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal relationships
<input type="checkbox"/>	Membership or active role in other organisations, e.g. societies, lobby or pressure groups, government agencies, etc.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Position of authority in an organisation, such that you are seen as upholding that organisation's views, standards, values, etc.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Being involved in other projects using in vitro systems and NAMs, as well as in risk assessment procedures issues described in the papers partially overlap and or are extremely useful for my current work

Signature

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Emanuele Cresto". The signature is written in a cursive style with a distinct loop at the end of the last name.

Notes

- (1) An "interest" is a commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice. A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another. Interests may be financial or non-financial.
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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebtox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. **Last updated: 20 December 2022**

Your name: Mathieu Vinken

Your email address: mathieu.vinken@vub.be

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 05/06/2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Final review

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to your situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

Do you, your family, close relations or acquaintances, currently have, have had in the last 5 years, or expect to have in the next 2 years, any financial interests (potential gains or losses) that could be affected by the publication?

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Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Insert here

Signature

A handwritten signature consisting of a vertical line on the right side, a horizontal line crossing it, and a loop on the left side.

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Evidence-Based Toxicology Declaration of Interests Form

This form was adapted from the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (www.ebttox.org) Declaration of Member Interests form. Last updated: 20 December 2022

Your name: Camilla Svendsen

Your email address: Camilla.svendsen@fhi.no

Date of completion of form (DD MMM YYYY): 20 June 2023

Contribution to the Publication Please describe in CRediT format

Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, data curation, visualisation

Interests Please place an X next to any interests relevant to you situation. See notes for term definitions.

Financial interests

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<input type="checkbox"/>	Other non-financial interests

Please provide details about the financial interests you have indicated above

None

Please provide details about the non-financial interests you have indicated above

Evidence-based chemical risk assessments are a large part of my daily work. There are a paradigm shift from using animal studies to using NAMs, also in chemical risk assessment. Therefore, I am interested in the development of tools for incorporation of data from NAMs as evidence in chemical risk assessments.

Signature

Notes

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